

ISic3432

I.Sicily inscription 3432

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Dianae Fons

Place of origin (modern)

Comiso

Provenance

necropoli di Via Tenente Meli

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Comiso, Scuola di Arte

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644827

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 467-468 no.13

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Manganaro, G. 1962. Graffiti e iscrizioni funerarie della Sicilia orientale. *Helikon*. 2: 485-501. At 500-501 fig.9

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